

of the literature shows that chrysophanic acid and rheochrysidin (physcion) have already been isolated from *R. orientalis*³. In the present paper, we report the isolation of nepodin (I), tricosanol (II), β -sitosterol (III) and emodin (IV) from the roots of this plant.

Pet. ether (60°-80°) extract of air-dried powdered roots was subjected to silicagel chromatography. Elution with Pet. ether-benzene (4 : 1) yielded compound (I) which crystallised as pale yellow needles from *n*-hexane m.p. 162°-163°. NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 2.52 s, -CH₃ protons ; 2.64 s, -COCH₃ protons ; 6.84 s, 4-H ; 7.44 d (J=9 Hz), 5-H and a multiplet between 6.8 and 7.0 due to 6-H and 7-H. MS : M⁺ 216 and other prominent peaks at m/e 201, 198, 155, 127 and 115. Its identity was finally confirmed as nepodin by mmp, Co-TLC and superposable IR. Diacetate m.p. 186-7°, identical with nepodin diacetate (CO-TLC, IR and mmp).

Further elution of the column led to the isolation of chrysophanic acid (Pet. ether-benzene 4 : 1) and physcion (Pet. ether-benzene 3 : 2). Combined benzene and benzene-chloroform (1 : 3) eluates yielded a residue giving positive L.B. test. This on rechromatography over silicagel column afforded compound (II) m. p. 73°-74° (Pet ether-benzene 3 : 1), which was identified as tricosanol (mmp and Co-TLC) by comparison with an authentic sample. Pet. ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluate yielded compound (III), m.p. 136°, identified as β -sitosterol by CO-TLC, IR and mmp.

Ether extract of the powdered roots was chromatographed over a silica gel column. Benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) eluate furnished compound (IV) m.p. 253-255°. It was identified as emodin by mmp, CO-TLC, superposable IR, NMR and MS which were identical with that reported for emodin⁴.

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Some 6:8-Dichloro-S-Substituted-2-Mercapto-3-Aryl (or Alkyl)-4-Quinazolones

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IN view of the broad spectrum biological activities associated with 4-quinazolones¹⁻⁵, it seemed of interest to synthesize 6 : 8-dichloro-s-substituted-2-mercapto-3-aryl (or alkyl)-4-quinazolone derivatives and evaluate them for their activities. The therapeutic effect of 4-quinazolone derivatives has been demonstrated in the case of siamian and avian malarial infections. The anticonvulsant properties of QZ-2(2-methyl-3-*o*-tolyl-4-quinazolone, available commercially as Melsedin) have been reported in mice, rats and dogs⁶⁻⁹. A potent anticonvulsant property of BDH 1880 (2-methyl-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-quinazolone hydrochloride) has been reported against matrazole induced convulsions in mice¹⁰.

The above findings have led the authors to synthesize some 6 : 8-dichloro-2-thio-3-aryl (or alkyl)-4-quinazolones by condensing aryl or alkyl-isothiocyanates with 3 : 5-dichloro-anthranilic acid in dry ethanol, and alkylating these 4(3H)-quinazolones with alkyl halides in alcoholic alkaline solution. That the alkylation occurred at the sulphur rather than the nitrogen atom was proved for a representative member of the series by hydrolysis to the corresponding mercaptan.

Experimental

6 : 8-Dichloro-2-thio-3-aryl (or alkyl)-4-quinazolones were prepared as described earlier¹¹.

6 : 8-Dichloro-2-(*N*, *N*-benzylphenylcarboxamidomethylthio)-3-phenyl-4-(3-*H*)quinazolone : 6:8-Dichloro-2-mercapto-3-phenyl-4-(3H) quinazolone (3.2 g) was dissolved in 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution and filtered. In the filtrate, *N*-benzylchloroacetanilide (2.8 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of ethanol was added and the mixture was stirred vigorously for one hour at room temperature. The crystalline product obtained was filtered, washed 3 or 4 times with water and then with a little ethanol. Finally it was recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 142°, yield 50%. (Found : N, 7.42 ; S, 5.66. C₂₉H₂₁Cl₂N₃O₂S requires N, 7.69 ; S, 5.86%),

Similarly, other 6 : 8-Dichloro-2-(*N,N*-disubstitutedcarboxamidomethylthio)-3-aryl (or alkyl)-4-(3H) quinazolones were prepared. They were crystallized from ethanol. Their yields, melting points and analytical results are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE—1 6 : 8-DICHLORO-2-(N, N-BENZYLPHENYL CARBOXAMIDOMETHYLTHIO)-3-ARYL (OR ALKYL)-4 (3H) QUINAZOLONES.

where, R = Aryl or Alkyl
Bz = Benzyl

Sl. No.	Aryl (or Alkyl) group R.	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Nitrogen, %	
				Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	142	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	7.42	7.69
2.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	104	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	7.28	7.49
3.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	270	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ Cl ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	7.92	7.23
4.	Ethyl	202	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	8.18	8.43

Yields of the compounds are found in the range of 50-70%. All the compounds were also analysed for S. The analytical results were within $\pm 0.3\%$ of the calculated values.

Similarly, various 6:8-dichloro-2-(N, N-diethyl carboxamidomethyl thio)-3-aryl (or alkyl)-4(3H) quinazolones were prepared and their yields, melting points and analytical datas are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE—2 6 : 8-DICHLORO-2-(N, N-DIETHYL CARBOXAMIDOMETHYLTHIO)-3-ARYL (OR ALKYL)-4(3H)-QUINAZOLONES.

Where, R = Aryl or alkyl

Sl. No.	Aryl (or Alkyl) group R.	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	Nitrogen, %	
				Found	Calcd.
1.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	218	C ₃₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ SCl ₂	9.06	9.33
2.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	268	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₂ SCl ₃	8.65	8.92
3.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	192	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₄ SCl ₂	8.80	9.01
4.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	234	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄ SCl ₂	8.51	8.75
5.	Ethyl	230	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ SCl ₂	10.50	10.82
6.	Butyl	276	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂ SCl ₂	9.80	10.09
7.	Benzyl	200	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ SCl ₂	9.10	9.33

6-8-Dichloro-2-(N,N-diethyl carboxamidomethylthio)-3-butyl-4-(3H)-quinazolones : In a conical flask 3.0 g of 6 : 8-dichloro-2-mercapto-3-butyl-4-(3 H)-quinazolone was dissolved in 1.02 g of sodium hydroxide solution in 100 ml water and N, N-diethylchloro-acetamide (1.64 ml) was added drop by drop at room temperature. The flask was shaken vigorously after each addition. When all N, N-diethylchloroacetamide was added, the flask was shaken for another 40 min. The product was separated, filtered, washed with water and finally with a little ethanol. It was recrystallized from ethanol-acetone (1 : 1) mixture, m.p. 276°, yield 60%. Found : N, 9.80 ; S, 7.40. C₁₈H₂₃Cl₂N₃O₂S requires N, 10.09 ; S, 7.69%.

Yields of the compounds are found in the range of 40-60%. All compounds were also analysed or S. The analytical results were within $\pm 0.35\%$ of the calculated values.

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Oxidations with Ammonium Hexanitratocerate(IV). Part I: Milligram Determination of Polycyclic Hydrocarbons

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THE small scale determination of hydrocarbon function has always attracted organic analytical chemists because of the slow reactivity of the function and the lack of a general procedure. Quick and direct methods have been given for the small scale determination of cyclic hydrocarbons¹⁻³. Recently the spectrophotometric⁴⁻⁶, gas chromatographic⁷ and fluorescence spectrum techniques⁸ have been applied for detection and determination of polycyclic hydrocarbons. Marletta⁹ has reviewed in detail the recent developments in the determination of aromatic polynuclear hydrocarbons.

Taking advantage of the oxidising capacity of ammonium hexanitratocerate (iv) in nitric acid medium, a quick, precise and accurate (within 0.3-0.85% error) method has been developed for the milligram determination of polycyclic hydrocarbons at room temperature (25°) within five minutes reaction time.

Experimental

Reagent :

0.1 M Ammonium hexanitratocerate (IV) solution was prepared in 0.5 M nitric acid solution. 0.025 M aqueous ferrous ammonium sulphate solution and 1M sulfuric acid solution were prepared from reagent grade chemicals. 0.001 M aqueous ferroin solution was used as indicator.

Sample solution

40-50 mg. of the hydrocarbon was dissolved in glacial acetic acid in a 100 ml measuring flask. All the hydrocarbons were either recrystallised from the proper solvent till a constant melting point is obtained or procured in the pure form.

Procedure :

Aliquots containing 1-5 mg of the sample were taken in a 100 ml. conical flask and 5 ml. of 0.1 M Ce(IV) solution was added to it. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for five minutes at room temperature (25°). The reaction was quenched by adding 10 ml 1M sulfuric acid and the content shaken for a minute. The unreacted Ce(IV) was titrated against standard Fe(II) using ferroin indicator. A blank was also run under identical conditions using all other reagents except for the sample. The recovery of the sample was calculated with the difference in the readings of Fe(II) for blank and the actual estimation.

$$\frac{\text{mg of hydrocarbon}}{\text{ml of 0.025 M Fe(ii) Soln} \times \text{Mol wt. of Hydrocarbon}} = \text{Molarity}$$

Results

Results obtained with the recommended procedure are given in the table. The effect of concentration of Ce(IV), varying amounts of hydrocarbon sample, reaction time and temperature was also studied for all the hydrocarbons. On the basis of stoichiometry and the identification of final oxidation products, it is established that all the hydrocarbons get oxidised to corresponding quinones.

The presence of phenols, amines, alcohols and aldehydes interfere in the estimation. However the oxidation of benzene is not possible with the recommended procedure.

TABLE : DETERMINATION OF POLYCYCLIC HYDROCARBONS WITH Ce(IV).

Compound	Amount taken (mg)	Amount recovered (mg)	Molarity	Deviation %
Naphthalene	1.0100	1.0140	6	+0.39
	3.0300	3.0409	-	+0.36
	5.0500	5.0662	-	+0.32
Anthracene	1.0600	1.0680	6	+0.75
	3.1800	3.1978	-	+0.56
	5.3000	5.3196	-	+0.37
Phenanthrene	1.2800	1.2876	6	+0.59
	3.8400	3.8584	-	+0.48
	5.1200	5.1379	-	+0.35
Acenaphthene	1.3400	1.3486	8	+0.64
	2.6800	2.6952	-	+0.57
	4.0200	4.0332	-	+0.33
Diphenyl	1.6200	1.6284	6	+0.51
	3.2400	3.2552	-	+0.47
	4.8600	4.8740	-	+0.29